

A Proposed Standard for Accuracy Computations

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ABSTRACT

Weapon accuracy is characterized by a CEP, the radius of a circle containing 50% of a set of impact points. The existing technology for estimating CEP's is a zoo of formulas, made to handle the spectrum of possible manifestations of the bivariate normal impact distribution. Confidence intervals for CEP estimates have existed only for a few specialized cases. To circumvent these difficulties, the author has developed an accurate, simple, yet general method for calculating CEP confidence intervals, but additionally reduces the complexity of CEP estimation to a single simple formula, which has improved accuracy and confidence. Finally, the author has developed a rapid series formula which integrates the bivariate normal distribution exactly.

BACKGROUND

The author first encountered this problem twelve years ago when working on Minuteman II. At that time, it was recognized that the existing accuracy calculus (e.g. collection of formulas employed for accuracy estimation) was in error by some 20%. Several investigations were instituted by various individuals and organizations. An over-abundance of recommendations by the various organizations and individuals were made; many of the recommendations were not very good. Perspective was lost in the ensuing confusion, and the original problem was never resolved.

In my opinion, the then-existing Rand-234 CEP calculus [1] had less problems than the alternatives being proposed by the so-called "experts", so it is not surprising to me that SAC let the issue die without resolution.

THE BIVARIATE NORMAL DISTRIBUTION

The central limit theorem states that the accumulation of independent error sources will tend to be normally distributed. In the two-dimensional case of downrange and crossrange miss, a bivariate normal distribution function is therefore appropriate. In the days before the personal computer this distribution function could not be integrated, so various approximations were developed. At this date a veritable zoo of formulas exists for calculating accuracy for various conditions.

EXACT INTEGRATION

The author began working in the F-16 arena in October of 1988. A co-worker one day expressed, "What I really want is to be able to integrate the bivariate normal distribution function." The author replied, "Gee, I solved that problem twelve years ago." The original solution, derived in 1975, was cleaned up and published internally by Cindy Smith of TRW [2].

CLOSED-FORM ESTIMATION

In 1975 the author derived a closed-form solution which approximates the integration formula to within 0.5% for most situations, and with in 3% in extreme situations. The existing formulas can produce errors of 25% (or more), depending upon the situation. While I recognize that some of the existing formulas can be "patched", I feel that another band-aid fix would only aggravate the complexity of the existing problem, which could be alternatively handled with the single compact set of formulas. The process involves the extraction of appropriate statistical parameters from the data sample, and combining them in a way which does not introduce errors in the final computation. Let (x_1, y_1) , (x_2, y_2) , ..., (x_n, y_n) represent the impact miss distances. Unbiased estimates of the first and second moments of down-range and cross-range miss distances are given by

$$\bar{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i / n \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{y} = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i / n \quad (2)$$

$$L_x^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 / n \quad (3)$$

$$L_y^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 / n \quad (4)$$

Three intermediate calculations are performed,

$$m = L_x^2 + L_y^2 \quad (5)$$

$$v = 2L_x^4 + 2L_y^4 - 2\bar{x}^4 - 2\bar{y}^4 \quad (6)$$

$$u = 2m^2/v \quad (7)$$

The estimate of CEP is given by

$$\hat{CEP} = \text{sqrt} [m (1 - 0.6804/v + .1345/v^2)] \quad (8)$$

The " $\hat{}$ " in Equation (8) is implanted to distinguish between the estimate of CEP and the true CEP.

DIFFICULTIES WITH EXISTING TECHNIQUES

In 1975 the "experts" were recommending robust estimators such as the median radial miss. My principal objection to these techniques is their associated *uncertainty*. I ran simulations employing normal distributions, and found the uncertainty to be twice as large when using the median estimator. This uncertainty increases greatly if the distribution is not normal, or if a few error sources tend to dominate. In application to Minuteman II, I remember that for a particular flight the median radial miss would have changed by over 35% if the next test flight would have impacted within the 50% circle. Fortunately (or unfortunately), the flight exhibited a gyro problem

and missed the target considerably. I do not have much confidence in estimators which can vary by 35% for a relatively mature system such as Minuteman II.

The original Rand-234 approximation was developed via curve fits. This method does not extend well for either eccentric distributions or distributions with large biases. None of the alternative methods take into account the effects of correlation, which can induce errors in CEP estimation of up to 25%. The original Rand-234 method has evolved into a joint military approved Joint Munitions Effectiveness Manual (JMEM, [1]). The Grubbs approximation [4], [5] was derived from a similar approach to the one proposed; it is, however, a less accurate, especially for small sample sizes.

METHOD COMPARISONS

The bivariate normal distribution function can be characterized by five parameters. These parameters are

- μ_x Down range miss bias
- μ_y Cross range miss bias
- σ_x Standard deviation of downrange miss
- σ_y Standard deviation of crossrange miss
- ρ Downrange/crossrange correlation.

A methodology can be performed only for specialized cases. Synthetic data sets for known conditions were generated via Monte Carlo Simulation, the CEP for each data set were then calculated, and the tabulated results are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

TABLE 1. METHODOLOGY FOR ECCENTRIC CASE
(four samples, $\mu_x=0, \mu_y=0, \sigma_x=\sigma_y/3$)

CEP Estimator	Relative Error (%)	
	Bias	Standard Deviation
Numerical Integration	8.8	33.2
Grubbs	14.2	34.9
JMEM	-2.7	33.3
Proposed	1.9	31.5

The proposed method scored better than all of the viable alternatives.

The eccentric case,

$$\sigma_x = \sigma_y/3 \quad (9)$$

is typical for weapon systems such as F-16 and Minuteman III. Crossrange dispersion is typically smaller because crossrange dispersion is easier to control than downrange dispersion. The synthetic data sets consisted of four samples. The number four was selected because 3 replicates are currently employed in verifying new weapon hardware and software for F-16.

TABLE 2. METHODOLOGY FOR CIRCULAR NORMAL CASE
(four samples, $\mu_x=0, \mu_y=0, \sigma_x=\sigma_y$).

CEP Estimator	Relative Error (%)	
	Bias	Standard Deviation
Numerical Integration	5.7	30.5
Grubbs	8.2	27.9
JMEM	-6.8	27.2
Proposed	-3.1	25.5
Circular Normal	-2.2	24.7

Circular Normal Case. In the circular normal case of

$$\mu_x = \mu_y = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma = \sigma_x = \sigma_y \quad (11)$$

there exists an associated circular normal CEP estimator,

$$\hat{CEP} = 1.1774 s \quad (12)$$

where

$$s^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^2 + y_i^2) / 2n \quad (13)$$

is an unbiased estimator of σ^2 . This estimator is optimal in the sense that it can be derived from a single statistical parameter, s . In terms of performance (see Table 2), the proposed estimator is nearly optimal.

The current JMEM standard [1] uses an estimator

$$\hat{CEP} = .587 (s_x + s_y) \quad (14)$$

where

$$s_x = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 / (n-1)} \quad (15)$$

$$s_y = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2 / (n-1)} \quad (16)$$

One impact point is effectively lost because information is removed to estimate the mean values of the downrange and crossrange miss. The proposed method does not have this deficiency. When testing individual weapons can exceed one million dollars, each, the inadvertent loss of a single drop through analytical method should not be tolerated.

The effect of biases are ignored in the existing JMEM accuracy calculus [1], the philosophy being that biases can be easily removed by fudging the flight software. Indeed. The resulting weapon accuracy is clouded by the uncertainty in the associated biases, and the ability to effectively compensate for them via software.

The Grubbs method and the numerical integration methods both scored extremely poorly. The principal cause of this poor performance is that these methods require the estimation of all four separate parameters, which are then employed to calculate a CEP.

METHOD COMPARISONS WHEN THE UNDERLYING POPULATION IS KNOWN

Error as a function of correlation is plotted in Figure 1. If one does not rotate to an uncorrelated reference frame, this error exists with any method employed. The relative error can be as much as 25%.

Error as a function of eccentricity is plotted in Figure 2. The proposed closed-form approximation has the best properties.

Error as a function of bias is plotted in Figure 3. Bias errors should not exceed dispersion (otherwise, the user should correct the targeting program). For bias errors less than one standard deviation, the proposed closed-form approximation has the best properties.

Figure 1. Relative Error in CEP Estimation vs Correlation

Figure 2. Relative Error in CEP Estimation vs Eccentricity

Figure 3. Relative Error in CEP vs Bias.

CALCULATING CONFIDENCE IN CEP ESTIMATES

Confidence intervals for CEP can be calculated from standard statistical tables assuming that $CEP^2 \times n \times \nu$ is approximated by a χ^2 distribution with $n \times \nu$ degrees of freedom. To evaluate the upper 95% confidence limit, look up the upper 1 tailed 95% confidence limit, Q for a χ -squared distribution with $n \times \nu$ degrees of freedom. The upper 95% confidence limit on CEP is

$$CEP_{upper} = CEP \times \sqrt{Q / (n \times \nu)} \quad (17)$$

For a circular normal case with 18 drops, $\nu=2$, so

$$CEP_{upper} = CEP \times \sqrt{51.0 / 36} \quad (18)$$

$$= CEP \times 1.19 \quad (19)$$

which is 19% higher than the sampled CEP.

NOMENCLATURE

Distributions are expressed in terms of a density function f . If R is a region about a point X_0 , and with area dA , then the probability of a point X will lie in the region R is given by the formula

$$P\{X \in R\} \approx f(X) dA \quad (20)$$

as the area of the region R becomes small, the relative error in Equation (20) goes to zero. For the two-dimensional case, the point

$$X = (x,y) \quad (21)$$

yields a density function,

$$f(X) = f(x,y) \quad (22)$$

which is sometimes qualified as $f_{x,y}(x,y)$.

The Bivariate Normal Distribution. The density function for the bivariate normal distribution is given by [6]

$$f(x,y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_x\sigma_y} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu_x)^2}{2\sigma_x^2} - \frac{(y-\mu_y)^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) \quad (23)$$

CEP BY INFINITE SERIES

An infinite series formula provides not only 50% probability circles, but can determine the probability of hitting within any arbitrary circle of radius R. For a given bivariate normal distribution, the probability of falling within a circle of radius R is given by the formula [6]

$$P(R) = \iint_{x^2+y^2 < R^2} \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_x\sigma_y} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu_x)^2}{2\sigma_x^2} - \frac{(y-\mu_y)^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) dy dx \quad (24)$$

In polar coordinates this can be expressed as

$$P(R) = \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_x\sigma_y} \exp\left(-\frac{(r\cos\theta-\mu_x)^2}{2\sigma_x^2} - \frac{(r\sin\theta-\mu_y)^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) d\theta dr \quad (25)$$

The approach to evaluating this integral is to factor out the constant terms, and then to expand the exponential function via Taylor series expansion. The resulting infinite series can then be integrated and factored. After integration, the series is still of exponential order, and converges very rapidly.

The constant term is

$$C = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_x\sigma_y} \exp\left(-\frac{\mu_x^2}{2\sigma_x^2} - \frac{\mu_y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) \quad (26)$$

The Taylor series expansion of the exponential is given by

$$\exp(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^i}{i!} \quad (27)$$

Substitution into Equation (25) yields

$$P(R) = C \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i!} \left[\frac{-r^2\cos^2\theta}{2\sigma_x^2} + \frac{r\mu_x\cos\theta}{\sigma_x} - \frac{-r^2\sin^2\theta}{2\sigma_y^2} + \frac{r\mu_y\sin\theta}{\sigma_y} \right]^i d\theta r dr \quad (28)$$

According to the Multinomial Expansion Theorem [7], a sum to any cardinal number k can be expressed

$$(u_1 + \dots + u_r)^i = \sum \frac{i!}{n_1! \dots n_r!} u_1^{n_1} \dots u_r^{n_r} \quad (29)$$

where the sum is taken over all cardinal numbers $n_1 \dots n_r$ satisfying

$$n_1 + \dots + n_r = i \quad (30)$$

Substituting into Equation (28),

$$P(R) = C \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^i \sum_{k=0}^j \sum_{m=0}^k \frac{1}{(i-j)!(j-k)!(k-m)!m!} \left(\frac{-r^2\cos^2\theta}{2\sigma_x^2}\right)^{i-j} \left(\frac{-r^2\sin^2\theta}{2\sigma_y^2}\right)^{j-k} \left(\frac{r\mu_x\cos\theta}{\sigma_x}\right)^{k-m} \left(\frac{r\mu_y\sin\theta}{\sigma_y}\right)^m d\theta r dr \quad (31)$$

Collecting terms,

$$P(R) = C \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^i \sum_{k=0}^j \sum_{m=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{i-k} r^{2i-k+1}}{(i-j)!(j-k)!(k-m)!m!} \frac{\cos^{2i-2j+k-m}\theta \sin^{2j-2k+m}\theta \mu_x^{k-m} \mu_y^m}{2^{2i-2k}\sigma_x^{2i-2j+2k-2m} \sigma_y^{2j-2k+2m}} d\theta dr \quad (32)$$

For u, v even,

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \cos^u\theta \sin^v\theta d\theta = \frac{u! v! 2\pi}{(u/2)!(v/2)!((u+v)/2)! 2^{u+v}} \quad (33)$$

The above integral is zero if either u or v is odd. The integration with respect to θ is zero unless k, m are both even. To eliminate the odd terms, substitute

$$k = 2\kappa \quad (34)$$

$$m = 2L \quad (35)$$

Substituting into Equation (32), and integrating with respect to r,

$$P(R) = C \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^i \sum_{k=0}^j \sum_{L=0}^k \frac{(-1)^i R^{2i-2\kappa+2}}{(i-j)!(j-2\kappa)!(2\kappa-2L)!(2L)!} \frac{(2i-2j+2\kappa-2L)!(2j-4\kappa+2L)! 2\pi}{(2i-2\kappa+2)!(i-j\kappa-L)!(j-2\kappa+L)!(i-\kappa)! 2^{1-\kappa}} \frac{\mu_x^{2\kappa-2L} \mu_y^{2L}}{2^{i-2\kappa}\sigma_x^{2i-2j+4\kappa-4L} \sigma_y^{2j-4\kappa+4L}} \quad (36)$$

It is not easy to evaluate the above series. First, one would like an easy method for deciding when one would like a formula which is symmetric in x and y. Changing the order of summation,

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^i \sum_{k=0}^j \sum_{L=0}^k \rightarrow \sum_{L=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\kappa=L}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{i=j}^{\infty} \quad (37)$$

Then make the substitutions,

$$J = \kappa - L \quad (38)$$

$$U = j - 2\kappa \quad (39)$$

$$V = i - j \quad (40)$$

(With the inverse relationships)

$$\kappa = J + L \quad (41)$$

$$j = U + 2\kappa \quad (42)$$

$$= U + 2J + 2L \quad (42)$$

$$i = V + j \quad (43)$$

$$= V + U + 2J + 2L \quad (43)$$

The order of summation becomes

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \rightarrow \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \sum_{v=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \quad (44)$$

Making the substitutions into Equation (36) and cancelling out a factor of 2,

$$P(R) = C \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{v=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{V+U} R^{2V+2U+2J+2L+2}}{V!U!(2J)!(2L)!} \frac{(2V+2J)!(2U+2L)! \pi}{(V+U+J+L+1)(V+J)!(U+L)!(V+U+J+L)!} \frac{\mu_x^{2J} \mu_y^{2L}}{2^{2V+2U+J+L} \sigma_x^{2V+4J} \sigma_y^{2U+4L}} \quad (45)$$

Then make the substitutions

$$U = K - L \quad (46)$$

$$V = I - J \quad (47)$$

A cursory examination of inverse relationships,

$$K = U + L \quad (48)$$

$$I = V + J \quad (49)$$

provides the order of summation

$$\sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{v=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \quad (50)$$

Substituting into Equation (45),

$$P(R) = C \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{I+K+L+J} R^{2I+2K+2}}{(I-J)!(K-L)!(2J)!(2L)!} \frac{(2I)!(2K)! \pi}{(I+K+1)! I! K!} \frac{\mu_x^{2J} \mu_y^{2L}}{2^{2I+2K-J-L} \sigma_x^{2I+2J} \sigma_y^{2K+2L}} \quad (51)$$

Factoring can greatly reduce the computation requirements. Substituting from Equation (26) and factoring,

$$P(R) = \frac{R^2}{2\sigma_x\sigma_y} \exp\left(\frac{-\mu_x^2}{2\sigma_x^2} - \frac{\mu_y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) \sum_{I=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2I)!}{(I+1)! I!} \left(\frac{-R^2}{4\sigma_x^2}\right)^I \left[\sum_{J=0}^I \frac{I!}{(I-J)!(2J)!} \left(\frac{-2\mu_x^2}{\sigma_x^2}\right)^J \right] \sum_{K=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2K)!}{(K+1)!(K)!} \left(\frac{-R^2}{4\sigma_y^2}\right)^K \frac{(I+1)!(K+1)!}{(I+K+1)!} \sum_{L=0}^K \frac{K!}{(K-L)!(2L)!} \left(\frac{-2\mu_y^2}{\sigma_y^2}\right)^L \quad (52)$$

Although Equation (52) contains more expressions than Equation (51), the combined factorial terms are more amenable to efficient recursive formulation.

Limitations

For the case

$$R \gg \sigma \quad (53)$$

the factors in Equation (52) of the form

$$\left(\frac{R^2}{\sigma^2}\right)^V \quad (54)$$

can become quite large, and exceed the floating point capacity of standard computers. For this reason, the implementation of Equation (52) can fail for extreme cases of eccentricity and bias. This limitation can be abstracted to

$$\frac{\min(\mu_x\mu_y/\sigma_x\sigma_y)}{\max(\sigma_x\sigma_y)} > 0.1 \quad (55)$$

The recommended closed-form approximation does not have this difficulty.

INVERSE PROBABILITY FUNCTION

Equation (52) gives miss probability as a function of radius. The inverse function is easily obtained via secant method [8]. Suppose we are an evaluation of two points, the probability function for two radii,

$$P(R_0) = P_0 \quad (56)$$

$$P(R) = P \quad (57)$$

we desire the radius \hat{R} ,

$$P(\hat{R}) = 0.5 \quad (58)$$

If one assumes approximate linearity of the function P, and estimate of R is given by

$$\hat{R} = R + \frac{(R_0 - R)(0.5 - P)}{(P_0 - P)} \quad (59)$$

The initial starting point for R is provided by the closed-form solution. The initial starting points R_0, P_0 are provided by

$$R_0 = P_0 = 0 \quad (60)$$

This saves computing an initial value because

$$P(0) = 0 \quad (61)$$

PROGRAM TO CALCULATE CEP USING INFINITE SERIES

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"Converges if  $\sigma_x/\sigma_y \geq 0.1$  and  $\sigma_y/\sigma_x > 0.1$ 
 $\mu_x = 0; \mu_y = 0; \sigma_x = 1; \sigma_y = 1$ 
loop
print "Enter  $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \mu_x, \mu_y$ "
read
 $\sigma_x = \text{val}()$  else exit
 $\sigma_y = \text{val}(); \mu_x = \text{val}(); \mu_y = \text{val}()$ 
 $\mu_x^2 = \mu_x * \mu_x; \mu_y^2 = \mu_y * \mu_y; \sigma_x^2 = \sigma_x * \sigma_x; \sigma_y^2 = \sigma_y * \sigma_y$ 
 $Rx^2 = \sigma_x^2 + \mu_x^2; Ry^2 = \sigma_y^2 + \mu_y^2$ 
"Use closed-form approximation for initial guess
 $m = Rx^2 + Ry^2$ 
 $v^2 = Rx^2 * Rx^2 + Ry^2 * Ry^2 - \mu_x^2 * \mu_x^2 - \mu_y^2 * \mu_y^2$ 
 $v = m * m / v^2$ 
print "m,v",m,v
 $CEP = \text{sqrt}(m * (1 - .6804/v + .1345/(v * v)))$ 
print " $\mu_x, \mu_y, \sigma_x, \sigma_y, \mu_x, \mu_y, \sigma_x, \sigma_y$ "
print "CEP", CEP
"Go do infinite series...calculate P(R)"
 $R_0 = 0; P_0 = 0$ 
 $R = CEP$ 
 $x_{bn} = -\mu_x^2 / \sigma_x^2; y_{bn} = -\mu_y^2 / \sigma_y^2$ 
 $C = \text{exp}((x_{bn} + y_{bn}) * 0.5) / (2 * \sigma_x * \sigma_y)$ 
loop
 $Rx = -.25 * R * R / \sigma_x^2; Ry = -.25 * R * R / \sigma_y^2$ 
 $F_{out} = C * R * R$ 
 $Prob = 0; Finl = 1; k = 0$ 
LOOP
 $T = 1; Q = 0; I = 0$ 
LOOP
 $Q = Q + T$ 
 $T = T * x_{bn} * (k - I) / ((I + 1) * (I + 1))$ 
IF  $\text{abs}(T) < 1.E-14$  then exit
 $I = I + 1$ 
IF  $I > k$  THEN EXIT
END

```

```

Fin = Fout*Q
IF ABS(Fin)+ABS(Fin) < 1.E-8 THEN EXIT
Finl = Fin
Fxl = 1
l = 0
LOOP
  T = 1;Q = 0;I = 0
  LOOP
    Q = Q + T
    T = T*bn*(1-I)/((I+1)*(I+1))
    IF abs(T) < 1.E-14 THEN EXIT
    I = I + 1
    IF I > 1 THEN EXIT
  END
  Fx = Q * Fin
  Prob = Prob + Fx
  IF ABS(Fx)+ABS(Fxl) < 1.E-8 THEN EXIT
  Fxl = Fx
  Fin = Fin * Ry*(I+1)/((I+1)*(I+k+2))
  l = l + 1
  IF l > 300 THEN k = 300;EXIT
END
Fout = Fout*Rx * (k+k+1)/((k+2)*(k+1))
k=k+1;IF k>300 THEN print "Divergence";EXIT
END
PRINT R,Prob
Rn = R + (R0-R) * (0.5 - Prob)/(PO - Prob)
IF ABS(Rn - R) < 1.E-6 THEN EXIT
RO = R;PO=Prob; R = Rn
end
print "CEP",Rn
end

```

ESTIMATING CEP FROM A SAMPLE

One major limitation of using the series formula for calculating CEP is that the underlying distribution parameters ($\mu_x, \mu_y, \sigma_x, \sigma_y$) are not known. The extraction of a viable CEP estimation process involves the extraction of appropriate statistical parameters from the data sample, and to combine them in a way which does not introduce errors in the final computation. If one is not careful, then the resulting CEP estimate can become biased, particularly for small data sets.

THE RADIAL IMPACT DISTRIBUTION

The bivariate normal distribution is an unwieldy animal, a function of five separate parameters. The approach, first developed by Grubbs [4,5] is to approximate the radial miss (squared) of the bivariate normal distribution with a simpler distribution with a similar shape. The distribution selected is the x -squared distribution function, which is a function of a single parameter, ν .

$$R^2 = \alpha x_\nu^2 \quad (62)$$

The matching is performed by matching the mean and variance of the radial miss (squared) with the appropriate x -squared distribution.

THE x^2 DISTRIBUTION

The x^2 distribution function is defined by the density function

$$f(t) = K t^{\nu/2-1} \exp(-t/2) \quad (63)$$

The variable ν is referred to as the degrees of freedom, and the constant K is defined so that the total probability of occurrence is one

$$\int_0^\infty K t^{\nu/2-1} \exp(-t/2) dt = 1 \quad (64)$$

The x^2 appears naturally in classical applications; principally, suppose that one takes ν independent normally variables with mean of zero, and variance of one. The resulting sum of squares of these variables is distributed as x^2 with ν degrees of freedom.

Application to the Radial Distribution. If the means are zero and the standard deviations are equal, then

$$R^2/\sigma^2 = x^2/\sigma^2 + y^2/\sigma^2 \quad (65)$$

is distributed as a x^2 with 2 degrees of freedom. Similarly, if one of the standard deviations, σ_y^2 is zero, then

$$R^2/\sigma_x^2 = x^2 / \sigma_x^2 \quad (66)$$

is distributed as x^2 with one degree of freedom. It is for this reason the the x^2 distribution was selected to fit the radial distribution.

OBTAINING CONFIDENCE IN CEP ESTIMATES.

Equation (8) can be expressed in the form,

$$\hat{CEP}^2 = \Lambda m \quad (67)$$

From Equation (5), m can be expressed as

$$m = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i^2 / n \quad (68)$$

Let us now examine the definition of a x^2 distribution. In particular, if $x[1], x[2], x[3], \dots$ are normally distributed with zero mean and variance, then the sum

$$x_k^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k x[i]^2 \quad (69)$$

is distributed as x^2 with k degrees of freedom. As a consequence of this definition, if $x_\nu[1]^2, x_\nu[2]^2, \dots$ are distributed as x^2 with ν degrees of freedom then it follows that

$$x_d^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n x_\nu[i]^2 \quad (70)$$

is distributed as x^2 with

$$d = n \times \nu \quad (71)$$

degrees of freedom.

Substituting from Equation (62), Equation (68), and Equation (67),

$$x_d^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i^2 / \alpha \quad (72)$$

$$= m \times n / \alpha \quad (73)$$

$$= CEP^2 \times n / (\alpha \Lambda) \quad (74)$$

Thus \hat{CEP}^2 is proportional to a x -squared variate with $d = \nu \times n$ degrees of freedom.

CLOSED-FORM APPROXIMATION

Overview. For the bivariate normal distribution, one derives formulas for the mean, M and variance, V of the squared radial miss, R^2 .

$$M = \lambda_x^2 + \lambda_y^2 \quad (75)$$

$$V = 2(\lambda_x^4 + \lambda_y^4 - \mu_x^4 - \mu_y^4) \quad (76)$$

where $\mu_x, \mu_y, \lambda_x, \lambda_y$ are the first and second moments of x- and y-components of miss,

$$\lambda_x^2 = \mu_x^2 + \sigma_x^2 \quad (77)$$

$$\lambda_y^2 = \mu_y^2 + \sigma_y^2 \quad (78)$$

The matching x^2 distribution with ν degrees of freedom has a mean of ν , and a variance of 2ν . Setting the two distributions equal to within a proportionality constant,

$$R^2 \approx \alpha x^2 \quad (79)$$

For special cases, the approximation is exact. By setting the means and variances equal,

$$M = \alpha \nu \quad (80)$$

$$V = 2 \alpha^2 \nu \quad (81)$$

Solving for α from Equation (81) and substituting into Equation (80)

$$\alpha = M/\nu \quad (82)$$

$$V = 2 (M/\nu)^2 \nu \quad (83)$$

Solving for ν ,

$$\nu = 2M^2/V \quad (84)$$

The 50% probability point, x_{CEP}^2 , of the x^2 distribution is obtained by curve fitting,

$$x_{CEP}^2 \approx \nu (1 - 0.6804/\nu + 0.1345/\nu^2) \quad (85)$$

Using Equation (79) to express CEP in terms of radial miss,

$$CEP \approx \sqrt{\alpha x_{CEP}^2} \quad (86)$$

Substituting for α from Equation (82)

$$CEP \approx \sqrt{M x_{CEP}^2/\nu} \quad (87)$$

Substituting from Equation (83),

$$\hat{CEP} = \sqrt{M (1 - 0.6804/\nu + 0.1345/\nu^2)} \quad (88)$$

The Expected Value Operator. If g is an arbitrary function of a random variable X , then an important feature of g is its expected value, defined by

$$E(g(X)) = \int_U g(X) f(X) dA \quad (89)$$

the integral is taken over the entire universe of possible occurrences of the random variable X . In mathematical terms, the expected value operator is a linear functional. This means that for arbitrary functions f and g that

$$E(f + g) = E(f) + E(g) \quad (90)$$

$$E(cf) = c E(f) \quad (91)$$

where c is any constant. Furthermore,

$$E(c) = \int_U c f(X) dA \quad (92)$$

$$= c \int_U f(X) dA \quad (93)$$

$$= c \quad (94)$$

First and Second Moments. The first and second moments of a random variable X are defined by

$$\mu = E(X) \quad (95)$$

$$\lambda^2 = E(X^2) \quad (96)$$

The first moment is the mean of the population. The second moment is related to the standard deviation, σ by the formula

$$\sigma^2 = \lambda^2 - \mu^2 \quad (97)$$

The number, σ^2 , is often referred to as the variance,

$$VAR(X) = E(X^2) - E(X)^2 \quad (98)$$

$$= \lambda^2 - \mu^2 \quad (99)$$

Variance Computations. If X is a random variable and α is a constant, examine the variance of the random variable

$$VAR(\alpha X) = E((\alpha X)^2) - E(\alpha X)^2 \quad (100)$$

From Equation (91),

$$VAR(\alpha X) = \alpha^2 E(X^2) - \alpha^2 E(X)^2 \quad (101)$$

$$= \alpha^2 VAR(X) \quad (102)$$

Supposing that two variables x and y are independent. The variance of their sum is computed

$$VAR(X+Y) = E((X+Y)^2) - E(X+Y)^2 \quad (103)$$

$$= E(X^2) + 2E(X)E(Y) + E(Y^2)$$

$$- E(X)^2 - 2E(X)E(Y) + E(Y)^2 \quad (104)$$

$$= VAR(X) + VAR(Y) \quad (105)$$

assuming independence of x and y .

Derivation of Radial Miss Properties. By definition,

$$R^2 = x^2 + y^2 \quad (106)$$

Mean Computation. The mean of R^2 is given by

$$M = E(R^2) \quad (107)$$

$$= E(x^2) + E(y^2) \quad (108)$$

$$= \lambda_x^2 + \lambda_y^2 \quad (109)$$

Variance Computation. The variance computation requires that we work in the uncorrelated frame (e.g., $\rho = 0$).

$$V = VAR(R^2) \quad (110)$$

$$= VAR(x^2 + y^2) \quad (111)$$

Uncorrelated normal variables are also independent. Applying Equation (105),

$$V = VAR(x^2) + VAR(y^2) \quad (112)$$

One notes that any normal variate X can be expressed as

$$X = \mu + W \sigma \quad (113)$$

where W is a normal variate with mean of zero and standard deviation of 1. Substituting Equation (113) into Equation (98),

$$VAR(X^2) = E(\mu^4 + 4\mu\sigma^3W + 6\mu^2\sigma^2W^2 + 4\mu\sigma^3W^3 + W^3\sigma^2 + W^4\sigma^4) - (\mu^4 + 2\mu^2\sigma^2 + \sigma^4) \quad (114)$$

Now the first, second, third, and fourth moments of a normal variable with zero mean and variance one are given by [6],

$$E(W) = 0 \quad (115)$$

$$E(W^2) = 1 \quad (116)$$

$$E(W^3) = 0 \quad (117)$$

$$E(W^4) = 3 \quad (118)$$

Substituting into Equation (114),

$$VAR(X^2) = \mu^4 + 6\mu^2\sigma^2 + 3\sigma^4 - \mu^4 - 2\mu^2\sigma^2 - \sigma^4 \quad (119)$$

$$= 2\sigma^4 + 2\mu^2\sigma^2 \quad (120)$$

Substituting from Equation (97),

$$VAR(X^2) = 2(\lambda^2 - \mu^2)^2 + 4(\lambda^2 - \mu^2)\mu^2 \quad (121)$$

$$= 2\lambda^4 - 4\mu^4 \quad (122)$$

Substitution into Equation (112) yields

$$V = 2(\lambda_x^4 + \lambda_y^4 - \mu_x^4 - \mu_y^4) \quad (123)$$

Transfer to Uncorrelated Reference Frame.

The effects of correlation ($\rho \neq 0$) can be removed by rotation to an uncorrelated frame of reference. In the non-zero case, the mean computation, Equation (109) is still valid, but the variance computation must be altered to

$$V = 2(\lambda_x^4 + \lambda_y^4 - \mu_x^4 - \mu_y^4) \quad (124)$$

$$+ 4\rho^2\sigma_x^2\sigma_y^2 + 8\rho\sigma_x\sigma_y\mu_x\mu_y \quad (125)$$

The derivation of Equation (125) takes some eight pages to document, and exceeds the scope of this paper. A purist is welcome to perform the operation manually. (The resulting answer is the same).

FITTING THE x^2 DISTRIBUTION

In classical applications, the degrees of freedom, ν always assumes an integral value. The formulation of Equation (64) is thus restricted. Evaluation of the x^2 distribution for non-integral values was performed by Taylor series expansion. The resulting tabulations are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3. 50% PROBABILITY LEVELS OF THE x^2 DISTRIBUTION

ν	x_{CEP}^2	ν	x_{CEP}^2	ν	x_{CEP}^2
1.0	.455	2.5	1.874	4	3.357
1.1	.542	2.6	1.972	5	4.351
1.2	.631	2.7	2.070	6	5.347
1.3	.722	2.8	2.169	8	7.340
1.4	.815	2.9	2.267	10	9.342
1.5	.908	3.0	2.366	12	11.340
1.6	1.003	3.1	2.465	14	13.338
1.7	1.098	3.2	2.564	16	15.338
1.8	1.193	3.3	2.662	18	17.338
1.9	1.290	3.4	2.761	20	19.338
2.0	1.386	3.5	2.860	30	29.336
2.1	1.483	3.6	2.960	40	39.335
2.2	1.581	3.7	3.059	50	49.335
2.3	1.678	3.8	3.158	100	99.334
2.4	1.776	3.9	3.257	200	199.334

Grubbs [5] uses the approximation taken from the National Bureau of Standards [6]. It yields

$$x_{CEP}^2 \approx \nu \left(1 - \frac{2}{9\nu}\right)^3 \quad (126)$$

However, (as the Bureau points out), this formula is not valid for $\nu < 30$. A typical value for this application is $1 < \nu < 3$. The values in Table 3 are more closely approximated by a curve given by the formula

$$x_{CEP}^2 - \nu = a + b/\nu \quad (127)$$

The coefficients, a,b are obtained by regression analysis, yielding a formula

$$x_{CEP}^2 \approx \nu (1 - 0.6804/\nu + 0.1345/\nu^2) \quad (128)$$

CONCLUSION

The proposed CEP estimation procedures are more accurate than the existing alternatives, and are directly amenable to evaluation of confidence.

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